

Prospective Study of Benign Breast Disease in Telangana Population**Kadaveru Prabhakar**

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Breasts have various disorders, like developmental abnormalities, epithelial and stromal proliferation, and inflammatory lesions. Neoplasm's patients with BBP have fear and anxiety about presuming that these lesions are malignant.**Method:** 55 (fifty-five) female adults aged between 20 to 60 years were studied. Routine blood examinations, radiological investigations (USG/mammography), and pathological investigations (FNAC/HPE / discharges) were also carried out wherever necessary.**Results:** 47 (85.4%) BBD from menarche to menopause, 6 (10.9%) in lactating, 2 (3.63%) in post-menopause 2 (3.6%) breast abscess, 5 (9.09%) in lactating women, 1 (1.8%) cold abscess, 2 (3.63%) cyclical mastalgia, 19 (34.5%) fibro-adenoma, 15 (27.2%) mastalgia, and 3 (5.45%) fibro-adenoma.**Conclusion:** As BBD is non-malignant and can be managed with medication. In resistant cases, surgery intervention is required. In certain cases, the clinician has to wait and watch.**Keywords:** (BBD), cold abscess, Fibro adenoma, mastalgia, tubular lesion, FNAC/HPE.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Though benign breast diseases are not malignant, patients have phobic states that these are malignant and end in death [1]. In fact, it is at least ten times more common than breast cancer. Up to 30% of women who suffer from BBD will require treatment at some point in their lives [2]. Clinical examination imaging studies like USG (ultrasonography) or mammography and pathological examination, like FNAC, or core needle biopsy, were done. Since the majority of benign lesions are not associated with an increased risk for subsequent breast cancer [3].

In BBD, unnecessary surgical procedures can be avoided. Making an early diagnosis and planning the treatment within 72 hours of the first consultation helps in alleviating unnecessary anxiety about breast cancer. Those BBDS patients with an increased risk of malignancy like atypical hyperplasia are given prompt treatment, a proper follow-up, and explained awareness regarding the risk of breast cancer [4]. Hence, an attempt at BBD with various pathological lesions in different age groups of females.

Material and Method

55 (Fifty five) adult females visited regularly the surgery department of TRR medical college hospital Inole Patancheru, Sangareddy (district), Telangana were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: Females with benign breast diseases like breast lumps, breast pain, nipple discharge, itching around the nipple, and axillary swelling, these patients gave their consent in writing for study were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: patients who had already undergone surgery and had breast cancer or immune compromised patients were excluded from the study.

Method: A detailed clinical examination and routine laboratory and radiological Investigations were carried out. All patients were taught "breast self-examination" by the principal investigator along with trained nurses. Radiological examinations were USG or mammography, and pathological investigation like FNAC, HPE, or discharge smear (if necessary).

The duration of the study was from April 2023 to March 2024.

Statistical analysis: Various findings of benign breast diseases, age distribution, and management were classified by percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Age distribution of benign breast disease (BBD) patients: 7 (12.7%) <20 years, 26 (47.2%) were 21–30 years of age, 15 (27.2%) were 31–40 years of age, and 5 (9.09%) were aged between 51–60 years of age.

Table 2: Classification of BBD according to menstrual age: 47 (85.4%) menarche to menopause (excluding pregnancy and lactation), 6 (10.9%) lactating, and 2 (3.63%) post-menopausal.

Table 3: Study of different types of Benign Breast diseases, Menarche to Menopause (excluding pregnancy and lactation) 2 (3.6%) breast abscesses, 1 (1.8%) cold abscess, 2 (3.63%) cyclical mastalgia, and 1 (1.8%) duct papilloma 1 (1.8%) Duct papilloma + Fibroadenoma 19 (34.5%)

fibroadenoma, 3 (5.45%) fibroadenosis, 1 (1.8%) galactocele, 15 (27.2%) mastalgia, 1 (1.8%) recurrent fibroadenoma, 1 (1.8%) tubercular lesion, Total 47 (85.4%) lactation, 5 (9.09%) had breast abscesses.

1 (1.8%) galactocele, Total 6 (36.3%) post-menopause, 1 (1.8%) fibroadenoma, 1 (1.8%) recurrent fibroadema

Table 4: Study of distribution Breast benign disease and nipple discharge

- Nipple distribution: 18 (33.7%) left, 22 (40%) right, and 15 (27.2%) both breasts.
- Study of Nipple Discharge 5 (9.09%) patients, 50 (90.9%) were absent.
- Treatment of BBD patients: 26 (47.2%) managed conservative 19 (34.5%) had surgery, and 10 (18.11%) waited and watched.

Table 1: Age Distribution in Benign Breast Disease patients

Age Distributions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 20	7	12.7
21-30	26	47.2
31-40	15	27.2
41-50	5	9.09
51-60	2	3.63

Figure 1: Age Distribution in Benign Breast Disease patients

Table 2: Classification of Benign Breast Diseases according to menstrual age

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
menarche to menopause age (excluding pregnancy and lactation)	47	85.4
Lactating	6	10.9
Post-Menopause	2	3.63

Figure 2: Classification of Benign Breast Diseases according to menstrual age

Table 3: Study of different type Benign Breast Disease (BBD)

Type of BBD	menarche to menopause age (excluding pregnancy and lactation) (47)	Lactating (6)	Post-Menopause (2)	Total
Breast Abscess	2 (3.63%)	5 (9.09%)	0	
Cold Abscess	1 (1.8%)	0	0	
Cyclical Mastalgia	2 (3.63%)	0	0	
Duct Papilloma	1 (1.8%)	0	0	
Duct papilloma + Fibro adenoma	1 (1.8%)	0	0	
Fibro adenoma	19 (34.5%)	0	1 (1.8%)	
Fibro adenoma	3 (5.45%)	0	0	
Galactocele	1 (1.8%)	1 (1.8%)	0	
Mastalgia	15 (27.2%)	0	0	
Recurrent fibroadenoma	1 (1.8%)	0	1 (1.8%)	
Tubercular lesion	1 (1.8%)	0	0	
Total	47 (85.4%)	6 (10.9%)	2 (2.6%)	

Figure 3: Study of different type Benign Breast Disease (BBD)

Table 4: Study of distribution of Breast in BD and Nipple discharge (a) Nipple distribution of BBD

Side of Breast	Incidence	Percentage (%)
Left	18	32.7
Right	22	40
Both side	15	27.2

Figure 4 (a): Study of distribution of Breast in BD and Nipple discharge

Table 4 (b): Study of Nipple discharge

Nipple discharge	Incidence	Percentage (%)
Present	5	9.09
Absent	50	90.9

Figure 4(b): Study of distribution of Breast in BD and Nipple discharge (b) Study of Nipple discharge

Table 4 (c): Treatment of BBD patients

Treatment	Incidence	Percentage (%)
Management	26	47.2
Surgery	19	34.5
Wait and watch	10	18.1

Figure 4(c): Study of distribution of Breast in BD and Nipple discharge (c) Treatment of BBD patients

Discussion

The present study of benign breast diseases in the Telangana population. The prevalence of BD was higher in 26 (47.2%) of 21–30-year-old females, followed by 31–40-year-olds, i.e., 15 (27.2%), and least in 50–60 years of age (Table 1). In the classification of BBP menarche to menopause (excluding lactation and pregnancy), 47 (85.4%), 6 (10.9%) lactating, and 2 (3.63%) post-menopause (Table 2). In menarche to menopause (excluding pregnancy and lactation), there were 2 (3.6%) breast abscesses and 1 (1.8%) cold abscess. The highest BBD was 19 (34.5%) fibroadenoma, followed by 15 (27.2%) mastalgia, 3 (5.45%) fibroadenosis, and 1 (1.8%) tubercular lesion. In lactating females, 5 (9%) breast abscesses and 1 (1.8%) galactocele were observed. In post-menopausal women, 1 (1.8%) fibroadenoma and 1 (1.8%) recurrent fibroadenoma were noted (Table 3).

Nipple distribution was in only 5 (9%), treatment of BBD included, 26 (47.2%) managed 19 (34.5%) surgery, and 10 (18.12%) watched and waited therapy

(Table 4). These findings were more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

In the present study, a higher incidence of BBD was observed in the age group between 20-30 years, followed by 31-40 years. These observations were also reported in many previous studies [8,9]. Hence, it can be hypothesized that variations in the levels of female hormone secretions may lead to BBD. As BBDs were observed after puberty, variations in the secretion of estrogen, progesterone, growth hormone of the pituitary, and corticosteroids during lactation on prolactin and oxytocin for ejection of milk might have influenced various BBDs like mastalgia, fibro-adenoma, fibro-adenosis, and galactocele. It was also observed that the majority of lactating mothers develop breast abscesses and nipple discharge [10].

Moreover, right-sided involvement is greater than left-sided involvement in benign breast diseases, but anatomically, the upper outer quadrant is the most frequent site of involvement due to the bulk of mammary tissue [11]. It can also be hypothesized that,

due to the more frequent movement of the right hand, mostly by females generally, there will be more lymphatic flow, which carries many pathological elements that may lead to a higher incidence of BBD on the right side rather than the left side. Most of the BBD patients responded to conservative treatments that were followed for 3–6 months and finally had favorable results.

It is reported that lymphocytic mastitis and the closely related entity of diabetic mastopathy are uncommon, benign breast diseases that are believed to be induced by auto-immune phenomena [12]. It is important to diagnose fat necrosis because it can often mimic carcinoma of the breast, though it is a rare (0.8%) phenomenon in breast tumors that show hemorrhage and multinucleated giant cells microscopically [13].

It was also observed that the majority of women belonged to low- to middle-income and underprivileged classes; hence, nutritional causes for aggravating BBD could not be ignored.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study of the clinical spectrum and management of benign breast diseases at different ages in women will be useful to radiologists, physicians, and surgeons because BBD has different modalities of treatment, like conservative treatment, surgery, or waiting and watching for 3 to 6 months. But this study demands further patho-physiological, genetic, nutritional, hormonal, and immunological study because the exact pathogenesis mechanisms of benign breast diseases are still unclear.

Limitation of study: Due to the remote location of the research centre, the small number of patients, and the lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

This research paper was approved by the Ethical Committee of TRR medical college hospital Inole Patanchery, Sangareddy (district) Telangana-502319.

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